

Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial activity of Schiff Base Metal Complexes

Shivraj S. Anjanikar

Department of Chemistry,

Sharadchandra College, Naigaon, District- Nanded MS- 431709, India.

Corresponding Author: Shivraj S. Anjanikar

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Abstract:

Metals complexes of Ni (II) and Hg (II) were synthesised with Schiff bases of quinoline derivatives. Newly synthesised metal complexes were characterized by their elemental analysis, magnetic moment, molar conductance along with electronic, thermal, infrared spectral analysis. Ni (II) and Hg (II) complexes of ligands 4-hydroxy-3-(1-((6-methylpyridin-2-yl)imino)ethyl)quinolin-2(1H)-one (L_1) and 4-hydroxy-3-(1-((4-methyl-3-nitropyridin-2-yl)imino)ethyl)quinolin-2(1H)-one (L_2) were subjected for their XRD Study. Ni (II) Complexes of L_1 and L_2 were assigned octahedral geometry while Hg (II) complexes of identical ligands hold tetrahedral geometry based on the magnetic, XRD and spectral studies. All of the developed complexes were examined for antibacterial and antifungal activity, and they all exhibited substantial results. The Ni (II) and Hg (II) complexes with ligand L_2 shown good activity when compared to the standard drugs utilized.

Keywords: Metal Complexes, Quinoline derivatives, Schiff bases and Biological Study.

Introduction:

Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes have gained prominence in coordination chemistry due to their ease of synthesis and versatile applications. The formation of Schiff base ligands was initially documented by Hugo Schiff in 1864. They are compounds that include an imine or azomethine functional group (-C=N-) and are produced by condensation of primary amines with carbonyl compounds. Their ease of synthesis, capacity to fine-tune their structure by altering either the amine or

the aldehyde/ketone precursor, and ability to coordinate with a wide range of metal ions have all contributed to their widespread use in both fundamental and practical chemistry. These complexes exhibit remarkable catalytic¹, biological² and fluorescent properties³, making them valuable in diverse fields.

Schiff base complexes exhibit exceptional catalytic properties. They are widely employed as both homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts in organic transformations, including oxidation⁴, reduction⁵,

polymerisation⁶, and C–C bond-forming reactions⁷. Transition metal complexes with Schiff base ligands, for example, are recognised as effective catalysts in epoxidation⁸ and polymerisation processes⁹. In addition to their Catalytic importance, A significant focus in Schiff base metal complexes pertains to their biological properties. The azomethine group is closely linked to various biological activities, such as antibacterial¹⁰, antifungal¹¹, antiviral¹², anticancer¹³, and anti-inflammatory effects¹⁴. Complexation with metal ions frequently amplifies these activities, as metal ions can enhance transport across cell membranes, increase bioavailability, or produce reactive species that interact with biological targets. Consequently, Schiff base metal complexes have been extensively studied as prospective therapeutic agents, especially in antimicrobial drug development, where resistance to traditional antibiotics remains a substantial global challenge. In view of these Present investigation focusses on the design and synthesis of novel Ni(II) and Hg(II) metal complexes derived from quinolone Schiff bases.

Material and Methods:

All compounds utilised were of analytical reagent quality, and solvents were purified through distillation prior to application. IR spectra were obtained

using KBr discs on a Shimadzu IR-470 Spectrometer. The elemental analysis was performed using the Thermo Fisher Scientific CHN/S/O analyser. The magnetic susceptibilities of complexes were measured at room temperature using the Gouy's method and the Sherwood scientific magnetic susceptibility balance, with distilled water as the calibrant. The molar conductance of metal complexes was measured using a Fisher Scientific conductometer. Molar conductance measurements were obtained using 0.001 M complex solutions in DMSO at room temperature. Thermal analysis was conducted on a Shimadzu thermo-analyzer. Melting points were calculated using the open capillary method and were uncorrected.

Procedure:

Preparation of Ligands (L₁-L₂):

The 3-Acetyl 4-hydroxy quinolin-2-one was prepared by refluxing methyl anthranilate with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of situ. Sodium ethoxide. This synthesized 3-Acetyl 4-hydroxy quinolin-2-one on condensation with substituted amino pyridine provides the targeted ligands (L₁-L₂) according to the technique outlined in our prior publication.¹⁵

General procedure of synthesis of metal complexes:

The synthesis of each complex is processed by taking 0.02 moles of ligand (L₁-L₂) in a round-bottomed flask containing 50ml of ethanol. The contents are heated for a few minutes followed by gradual addition of 0.01 moles of solution of metal salt dissolved in 20ml of ethanol and added gradually in a hot solution of ligand. The contents are refluxed for two hours and cooled. A freshly prepared 10% alcoholic

ammonia solution is progressively added in a cold container with refluxed contents with constant stirring. At a particular pH, precipitation appears.

The precipitate of complex is digested for one hour. Any change in pH, if observed, is adjusted and further digested for an hour. The digested precipitate of a complex is filtered in hot, washed with alcohol (hot), followed by petroleum ether (40–60°C) and dried in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride.

Reaction Scheme:

Fig. 1 Synthesis of Metal Complexes of Ni(II) and Hg(II)

Anti-Bacterial Activity:

The agar well diffusion method was used to test the antibacterial activity.¹⁶ Mueller Hinton Agar for bacteria was used for all tests for antibacterial activity. For positive control of bacteria Ampicillin was used.

The solvent and positive control used was DMSO. Antibiotics and dehydrated media powder were brought from Hi-Media, India. Using sterile wire-loop, test organisms were aseptically added to sterile MH broth before being incubated at 37°C for 18 hours. This suspension

was utilized as an inoculant. Wells in the media plates with a 10mm diameter were made using a sterile cork borer for the addition of compound solutions and controls. With the aid of a micropipette, 100 µl of the compound solution was aseptically added to the wells to reach a final concentration of 10 g of compound in each well. As controls, the same quantity of DMSO and ampicillin solution were introduced. The plates were cooled for 30 minutes to allow solutions to diffuse through the agar substrate. Plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. *Bacillus subtilis* and *Salmonella typhi* were gram positive bacteria that were utilized as test organisms, whereas *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* were gram negative microorganisms. The zone margin should be regarded as the region that does not clearly display any expansion that the unaided eye can see. With a measuring scale in millimetres, the clean zone was measured

Antifungal Activity:

The poison plate approach was used to provide antifungal activity.¹⁷ For the evaluation of antifungal activities, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium moneliforme*, and *Penicillium chrysogenum* species were selected. Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) media was utilized as a culture. To sterilize the medium, it was autoclaved at 121°C for 25 minutes under 15 psi of pressure. 20 ml of sterilized, melted PDA was added to sterilized petri plates with 2 ml of each component, and the mixture was then gently stirred in a circular motion to get homogenized. With positive Neomycin and negative DMSO controls, the identical process was followed. The fungal spores from the slant culture were transferred to a test tube containing sterile saline and thoroughly mixed with a sterile wire loop. As an inoculant, this spore solution was employed. The plates were incubated for four days at room temperature. After incubation, the growth of the infected fungi was monitored on the plates. The outcomes were noted.

Table No. 1 Elemental Analysis of Ni (II) and Hg(II)Complexes

S. No	Complexes	Molecular formula	Colour	M.P. ^o C	Mol. Wt.	Conductivity μ_v	Elemental analysis Found (Calculated)			
							%C	%H	%N	%M
1	[Ni (L ₁) ₂]	[Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Greenish Yellow	248	679.36	16.26	60.02 (60.11)	4.54 (4.75)	12.30 (12.37)	8.58 (8.64)
2	[Ni (L ₂) ₂]	[Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish Green	252	769.35	12.09	53.02 (53.08)	3.88 (3.93)	14.48 (14.56)	7.66 (7.63)
3	[Hg(L ₁) ₂]	[Hg(C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂) ₂]	White	>300	785.23	16.02	51.88 (52.01)	3.63 (3.59)	10.60 (10.70)	25.61 (25.55)
4	[Hg(L ₂) ₂]	[Hg(C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄) ₂]	White	>300	843.29	11.88	46.58 (46.66)	3.02 (2.99)	12.74 (12.80)	22.90 (22.92)

Table No. 2 Electronic Spectral Data of Ni (II) Complexes

Sr. No.	Complexes of Ligand (L ₁ - L ₂)	Absorption Maxima cm ⁻¹ (nm)		
		V ₁	V ₂	V ₃
1	Ni [(L ₁) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	11360 (880)	16390 (610)	26315 (380)
2	Ni[(L ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	11235 (890)	16670 (600)	25640 (390)

Table No. 3 Magnetic Susceptibility Data of Ni (II) Complexes

Sr. No.	Ni (II) Complexes of ligand	$\chi_M \times 10^6$ (CGS)	$\chi_A \times 10^6$ (CGS)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
1	Ni [(L ₁) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3675.57	3974.77	3.08
2	Ni[(L ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	4284.50	4646.22	3.33

Table No. 4 Infrared Absorption Frequencies (cm⁻¹)

Sr. No.	Ligand / Complex	Bond vibrational modes (stretching – ν (cm ⁻¹))					
		Lactam	Pyridine	Azo-methine	Enolic	New Peaks	
		(C=O)	(C=N)	(C=N)↓	(C-O)↑	M-O	M-N
1	Ni [(L ₁) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1664	1604	1599	1270	497	442
2	Ni[(L ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1665	1603	1593	1276	472	430
3	Hg(L ₁) ₂	1665	1603	1583	1277	498	452
4	Hg(L ₂) ₂	1663	1600	1590	1279	486	447

Table No.5 Anti- Bacterial and Anti-Fungal Activity

Synthesized Schiff base ligands	Antibacterial Study Zone of Inhibition (diameter in mm)				Antifungal Study Growth of Fungi			
	Gram Positive		Gram Negative		A. niger	A. flavus	F. moniliforme	P. chrysogenum
	S. typhi	B. subtilis	E. coli	S. aureus				
Ampicillin (Reference)	18	19	17	18	Neomycin (Reference)	-	-	-
Ni [(L ₁) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	18	18	19	18	-	-	-	-
Ni[(L ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	20	22	20	20	-	-	+	-
Hg(L ₅) ₂	14	16	14	17	++	+	+	+
Hg(L ₅) ₂	18	19	18	20	-	-	+	-

Moderate growth (++) , Reduced growth (+) and No growth (-) of fungi

Result And Discussion:

All Nickel complexes synthesised in this study exhibit a greenish-yellow. They exhibit significant solubility in dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The low conductivity values of the complexes in DMSO signify their non-electrolytic characteristics.¹⁸The elemental analysis data of metal complexes confirm the ligand to the metal ratio for Nickel complexes as 2:1, proposing a monomeric complex. Mercury complexes are found colourless. They remain stable in air and moisture. The Hg(II) complexes decompose at high temperature (above 300°C). They are insoluble in non-polar and common polar solvents. At a very low concentration, solutions can be

prepared in methanol and DMSO. The molar conductance value of the complexes in DMSO (10⁻³M) is very low (11.20 -16.02 mhos⁻¹ cm²mol⁻¹), indicating the non-electrolytic nature of complexes. The metal to ligand ratio was shown as 1:2, predicting a monomeric structure. The colour, melting/decomposition temperature, conductivity measurement and elemental analysis of Ni (II), Hg (II) complexes synthesized from ligand L₁ - L₂ are presented in the table - 1.

The electronic spectra of Ni(II) complexes observed in the present work show absorption bands in three regions. V₁ = 11360-11235 cm⁻¹, V₂ = 16670 - 16390 cm⁻¹ and V₃ = 26315-25640 cm⁻¹. These observed bands may be assigned to three spin allowed transition

${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ charge transfer band respectively, which are characteristic of the distorted octahedral field.¹⁹ The electronic spectral data of Ni(II) complex with their L_1 and L_2 ligands are presented in Table -2 & fig-1&2.

The magnetic moment values μ_{eff} of all Nickel (II) complexes in the study were determined to be in the range. 3.08-3.33 B.M., agreeing to two unpaired electrons.²⁰ Their spectral data are presented in Table -3 while all Hg (II) complexes are diamagnetic.²¹

The crystal lattice parameters of the Ni(II), Hg(II) complexes with ligand L_1 were determined by the X-ray diffraction powder method. The X-ray diffraction patterns of complexes were recorded in the 2θ range from 10° to 80° . Based on the results and the literature support, the complexes with ligands are crystalline due to sharp reflexes shown, Fig.-3 & 4 and have been assigned monoclinic.²²

In the IR spectra of the corresponding metal complexes are reported in table - 4, medium to weak bands appeared in the region $1599-1583 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were assigned to C=N stretching vibration mode.²³ The medium intensity absorption bands in the region $1279-1270 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of metal complexes were predictable to enolic C-O stretching

frequency.²⁴ The band assigned to the lactam C=O stretching frequencies in the corresponding complexes were observed in the $1665-1653 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The metal complexes of Ni(II) in the present research show a broad band in the region $3500-2600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is attributed to the coordinated water present in these complexes.²⁵ Such bands are not observed in IR spectra of Hg(II) complexes. However, a peak observed in all the spectra in the range $3431-3249 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to -N-H stretching. (Fig. 5-6)

Based on conductivity, elemental and metal analysis, magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of the complexes, it is proposed that the Ni(II) complexes in the present investigation are having an octahedral configuration while Mercury complexes have tetrahedral geometry.

Fig-1

Fig-2

Fig-3

Fig-4

IR Spectrum of Hg (II) Complex of Ligand L₁

Fig-5

IR spectrum of Ni(II) Complex of Ligand L₁

Fig-6

Fig-7

The synthesized complexes of Ni (II) and Hg (II) were subjected for evaluation of antimicrobial activity. The findings are reported in Table 5. Metal complexes of Ni (II) and Hg (II) have demonstrated good antibacterial activity with all bacterial species in the range of 22-14 mm diameter of zone of inhibition. The antifungal test of metal complexes with all ligands revealed that they exhibit significant activity. The antibacterial and antifungal activity observed in complexes of Ni (II) and Hg (II) with ligands (L₂) is higher which might be due to presence of Nitro group in the moiety.²⁶

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we reported the synthesis, characterization, and antibacterial activity of metal complexes of Ni (II) and Hg (II) with Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic moieties, that include pyridine and quinoline derivatives, in order to contribute to coordination chemistry. While Hg (II) complexes are monomeric with tetrahedral geometry, Ni (II) synthesised metal complexes are monomeric and have an octahedral geometry. All of the complexes showed strong antibacterial and antifungal activity, corresponding to their antimicrobial analysis.

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